

Emojis as Digital Language and its Effect on Semantics

Maryam Khan

MS Linguistics, Riphah International University, Islamabad

Dr. Rukaiza Khan

Assistant Professor, Department of Basic Sciences & Humanities, NUST, Islamabad

Dr. Farooq Ahmed

Lecturer, Department of English MUST, AJK

Erum Maharvi

Assistant Professor, Department of English Linguistics, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur

Dr. Arif Hussain

Associate Professor, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, Pakistan

arifhussain@awkum.edu.pk

ABSTRACT: Emojis have gained prominence in interactive digital communication. These symbols are widely known and commonly recognized among computer-mediated communication (CMC) users. These digital signs are taken as a substitution for the non-verbal clues that are missing from CMC in comparison to face-to-face communication. People incorporate them in short texts they send or post because they cushion the feeling expressions. Despite their wide use, the understanding of their usage in a correct manner is still lacking. This study investigates the understanding of the usage of emoticons and emojis in text messages. The aim of this study is to determine whether any universal understanding of emoticons and emojis exists when there are thousands of people integrating them every day when disseminating text messages. For the purposes of this study, a survey form was utilized to gather information from students of different universities. Our results have concluded that though there is always a need for emojis to support the message emotionally; plain text can explain a major part of the semantics of the message. The results also established the fact that people have sense enough to use emojis to express emotions.

Keywords: Semantics, Text Message, Emoji, Symbols, Emoticon, Computer-Mediated Communication

[Introduction](#)

[Literature Review](#)

[Methodology](#)

[Discussion](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

The internet has transformed the way we communicate virtually. It has introduced the new-age hieroglyphic languages, emoticons and emojis. With the help of these new online modes of communication, we can now translate body language and verbal tone into the text over the internet. Emoticons, as pictorial icons, are predecessors of emojis. These are mainly a presentation of punctuation marks, letters and numbers that display sentiments. Emojis, on the other hand, are a recent invention in online communication. These are pictographs of faces, symbols, figures and objects (Grannan, 2017). The emojis have filled the gap and made electronic language emotionally rich despite the fact that it is part of non-verbal communication. It is also pertinent to know that the contribution of non-verbal information and prosodic features in our communication is greater than the

contribution of pure linguistic features in our real-life face-to-face interaction (Amaghlobeli, 2012). For this reason, the significance of emojis has been multiplied as they cushion prosodic features such as intonation, rhythm, and volume in online communication. These cryptograms are the paralanguage of the internet. They incorporate mood swings and add expressions of irony, pun, sarcasm and laughter (Hart, 2012). Emojis function as apparatus of digital communication and they make up for the inability of internet plain language of conveying facial expressions, body gestures and tone of voice (Lucas, 2016). Emojis are used more and more frequently in network communication, and the way they are used is becoming more and more diversified as well. They not only have unique semantic and emotional features but are also closely related to marketing, law, health care, and many other areas. The investigation of emojis has become a prolific subject in academia, the scholars from the fields of computing, communication, marketing, behavioral science and many other fields are studying them.

2. Literature Review

Wolf (2000) noted that “men and women used emoticons for different purposes. Men tended to use emoticons in a sarcastic or teasing manner, whereas women tended to use emoticons more often when they were attempting to communicate humorous messages.”

We reviewed the extent of the present body of research on emoji and noted the development, usage, function, and application of emoji with the purview that how emojis have been created, how they are used differently, what functions they have and what research has been conducted on them in different fields of studies.

A study by Seyednezhad, Fede, Herrera, and Menezes (2018) analyzed emojis in terms of sentiments and semantics. Different tweets about different subjects formed the data for this study. The study developed a bipartite network from the words and emojis extracted from the 6 collections of tweets on diverse topics. This network was used to analyze the sentiments, semantics, and position of emojis. The results showed that emojis were generally used in a positive sentiment, but the semantics of these emojis differ depending on the conversation.

Another research carried out by Amaghlobeli (2012) signified the importance of emojis and emoticons in text and their role as a verbal parameter. It dealt with typographic emoticons as linguistic units and observed their structures and uses in sentences. The research corpus covered 258 French text messages collected with anonymous questionnaires around the years 2008 – 2009. After providing age (17 to 35 years), gender and professional informants were asked to copy 3 or 5 SMS from their mobile phones into the questionnaires. After a graphic analysis of typographic emoticons, the result showed emoticon structure as a pictogram-like unit formed with alpha grams and topo grams of unique significative function, and visually conditioned to the referent. The morphological analysis had shown that, in emoticon structure, graphemes of entirely different significances and functions become morpheme-like units, which, like word morphemes, can be derivational, inflectional, or abbreviated, but never unbound. The analysis showed that emoticons are not only para-verbal devices, but also structural markers, and they play a significant role in the formation of the sentence.

An investigation by Walther and D'addario (2001) sought to determine the effects of three common emoticons on message interpretations. Hypotheses drawn from the literature on non-verbal communication reflected several significant relationships between emoticons and verbal messages. An experiment was conducted to assess affective and attitude interpretations of emoticon combinations with verbal phrases. The results showed that the contribution of emoticons in online communication is more than the verbal content. It was also found that the negative graphics shift the interpretation to negative meanings (Novak, Smailović, Sluban, & Mozetič, 2015). The data was collected for 1.6 million tweets across 13 European languages. In this data, 4% of the tweets consisted of emojis. The findings revealed that emojis express the speaker's emotional state as an independent channel of communication from that of the linguistic text. To examine the effect of emojis on communication via social media, Suresh (2018) found that WhatsApp is the most common social media channel where emojis are used to be interactive. The study also showed that youngsters have more updated knowledge of the use of emojis and emoticons.

There is another research conducted by Dürscheid and Silver (2017). It overviewed the functions of emojis in everyday written communication either a strategy of complementing or replacing the text. The study revealed that emojis do not have reference functions generally and they rarely replace the verbal part of communication. Kelly (2015) investigated the understanding of emojis and emoticons in text messages, and it found that emojis and emoticons don't have any inherent meanings. The meanings conveyed by them depend on context and situation. Therefore, the semantics of emoji is not universal. The present study also aims to analyze various aspects of emojis and their use for people in different geographical locations around the globe.

Chuchu Liu, et al (2021), published an article; 'Improving sentiments analysis accuracy with emoji embedding' and discussed about the challenging task of categorizing individual emotions from online texts in Chinese. They used a new source of emojis being used to express emotions during online conversations and analyzed popular sentiments being expressed in form of emojis. The authors incorporated emojis as a new source of sentiment and developed an improved model called CEmo-LSTM. The study highlighted that the emojis are effective in refining sentiment analysis algorithms and that the pandemic (COVID -19) impacted individual sentiments. Moreover, the study shows that the novel emoji-embedding algorithm combined emojis and emoji usage with the sentiment analysis model in an effective and efficient manner.

Vikas Arya, Deepa Sethi and Hemraj Verma (2018), conducted a study – 'Are emojis fascinating brand value more than textual language? Mediating role of brand communication to SNS and brand attachment' to examine the relationship between consumers' involvement on social media sites (SNSs) and their connection to a brand. The study highlighted the role of emojis as a significant moderator in this relationship. The data was collected from 252 respondents in India through online survey forms and physical questionnaires. The study found that brand communication mediated the relationship between consumer engagement on SNSs and brand attachment, and the availability of emojis acted as a mediating moderator, significantly impacting consumers' brand attachment behavior through brand communication. Nevertheless, the study contributed an original insight into understanding consumer brand attachment behavior on SNSs.

Faryal Qureshi, et al (2021), published a paper – ‘An analysis of the Emoji’s impact on the language and expressions of youth on social media’ to find out the impression of emojis on the language, thinking pattern and expressions of people during their communication on social media and day to day interactions. The study was conducted by collecting data from 130 participants between the age group of 16-35 in form of questionnaires and graphical representations. The study found that the augmented use of emojis in digital communication on social media has converted it into a colorful and friendly interface while reducing the use of written language. The study specified that emojis work as a tool to express feelings and thoughts of a person in text messages and have become a need of many people in making their conversations more colorful and interesting.

Ying Tang & Khe Foon Hew (2019), published a paper under the title, ‘Emoticon, Emoji, and Sticker Use in Computer-Mediated Communication: A Review of Theories and Research Findings’ and provided a methodical review of theories and empirical research about the use of emoticons, emoji, and stickers in computer-mediated communication. The researchers collected 51 articles from 11 databases in the fields of communication, linguistics, and psychology between 1996 and 2017. The study explained the definitions of emoticons, emoji, and stickers. Moreover, it presented a scheme for classifying theories/models into two main categories, and highlighted the main research findings on why and how people use these elements and their effects on communication.

Burhanuddin Arfah & Muhammad Hasyim (2020), conducted research on – ‘Linguistic functions of emoji in social media communication’ to find out the linguistic function of emojis in WhatsApp conversations. The study was based on the Barthes and Morris’s semiotic approach. The researchers collected data through online questionnaires, screenshots of different WhatsApp conversations. The study established that emojis are a part of grammatical components of language in social media communications. Moreover, the study provided insights into the use and importance of emojis in online communication and highlighted their role as an integral part of the language on social media.

Emmanouela (2021), published a reaserch article; ‘Emoji Use in Computer-Mediated Communication’ to provide a critical review of extant knowledge on emoji use in Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC). The study is a compilation of 46 empirical studies published between 1998 and 2020. The article provides a critical review and a summary table that reports the methodology, sample, key findings, user status and context in which the emojis have been used. The research findings are based on user status (i.e. individuals who use emojis vs. individuals who view emojis). Moreover, the study represents the effect of emojis in both personal and business contexts in Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC).

3. Methodology

Research Design

Under the quantitative data collection and qualitative analysis, the present research questions have been addressed and the study has adopted a parallel mixed-method design (Teddle & Tashakkori, 2009). Moreover, in line with other mixed-method researches (e.g., Teddlie, Reynolds, & Pol, 2000), the current study has been carried out in a pragmatist

paradigm. Mixed method researchers advocate the use of “whatever methodological tools are required to answer the questions under study” (Teddlie & Tashakori, 2009, p. 7). As a result, the paradigm of pragmatism frequently underlies studies adopting mixed-method approaches. Pragmatism has been described by Tashakkori & Teddlie (2003) as:

A deconstructive paradigm that debunks concepts such as “truth” and “reality” and focuses instead on “what works” as the truth regarding the research questions under investigation. Pragmatism rejects the either/ or choices associated with the paradigm wars, advocates for the use of mixed methods in research, and acknowledges that the values of the researcher play a large role in the interpretation of results. (p. 713)

Sampling and Data collection:

The purpose of our study was to know whether there is a universal understanding of emoticons and emojis, which is important considering the number of people using them every day when sending text messages. For this purpose, we made our questionnaire which consisted of two parts. The first part was the demography of the students which includes their Gender, Age and institutions. And the second part was consisted of 6 images in which respondents have to describe their state in 3 ways i.e.

1. Express your state of mind using, " TEXT + Emojis ",
2. Express your state of mind using, "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) and
3. Express your state of mind using, "ONLY ONE EMOJI".

In the second part questions were open-ended and respondents answered the question according to their state of mind. There was total 49 students who participated in our survey so there were 49 responses which were analyzed after the observation of the researchers.

Analysis

In our study, we used SPSS for all the analysis. The analysis includes the descriptive of the study (Table 1) in which we find out the Mean and standard deviations of the demography of students and the Frequency tables shows the Frequency, Percent, Valid percent and Cumulative percent of the Gender, Age and institutions individually. (Table 2), (Table 3), (Table 4). We graphically presented our data so that the study can be seen in one diagram (Figure1). After that, we performed Linear regression analysis through which we came to know the correlation coefficient relationship between Texts and emojis and the total percentage so that we know the variation in Text explained by the Emojis. Moreover, these relationships are also explained in the Line charts. Next, we test the hypothesis to determine if it follows that there is enough statistical proof for the study.

Table1
Descriptive statistics

		Gender	Institute	Age
N	Valid	49	49	49
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		1.1224	1.2653	1.5102
Std. Deviation		.33120	.44607	.50508

49 responses are shown in the table in which 1.1224 is the mean of Gender with 0.33120 standard deviation, 1.2653 is the mean of Institutions with 0.44607 standard deviation and 1.5102 is the mean of Age with 0.50508 standard deviation. Frequencies and percentages of each of them are shown below

Table 2
Descriptive of male and female

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	43	87.8	87.8	87.8
	Female	6	12.2	12.2	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Results show that there were 49 participants in which 43 were Male students. It means 87.8% participants were Male. 6 were females which means only 12.2% of them were females.

Table 3
Descriptive of Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15-20Years	24	49.0	49.0	49.0
	21-25Years	25	51.0	51.0	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Table 4
Descriptive of Institutes

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NUST college of EME	36	73.5	73.5	73.5
	Ripah international university	13	26.5	26.5	100.0
	Total	49	100.0	100.0	

Figure1
Graphical representation

Next, we have performed Liner regression Analysis which is used to estimate the relationship between two quantitative variables. We have applied Simple linear regression through which we came to know the relationship between Texts and Emojis. We have taken Text as a dependent variable and Emojis as an explanatory variable. This showed how the dependent variable (Text) got changed as the independent variable (Emojis) changed. We individually applied the test in our 6 images answers in order to take 6 evidences.

Table 5
Regression Analysis on Image 1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.607 ^a	.679	.655	814.767

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q4b Image1; Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"

This table provides the R (correlation coefficient) and R2 values. The R-value expresses the simple correlation which is 0.607 so it is a strong degree of correlation. The

R2 concludes that 68% of the total variation in the Texts (dependent variable) representing by the Emoji (independent variable). The result indicates that variation is valid, and people express their state of mind in texts with the 68% use of emojis.

Figure 2

Line chart of Image 1

This figure shows what countenance has been expressed by the students with what emojis. As we can see respondents express the biases of media by using sad and shocked emojis after it angry emoji and then with the usage of confused emoji. As well as respondents show that they are feeling sad and horrified with above-mentioned emojis, and moreover some of the respondents say they are disappointed and express their emotions with the usage of these mentioned emojis.

Table 6

Regression Analysis on Image 2

Model Summary				
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.513 ^a	.553	.549	589.729

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q5b Image2;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"

This table also provides the R (correlation coefficient) and R2 values. The R-value expresses the simple correlation which is 0.513 so it is a good degree of correlation. The R2 concludes that 55% of the total variation in the Texts (dependent variable) is

represented by the Emoji (independent variable). The result indicates that variation is valid, and people express their state of mind in texts with the 55% use of emojis.

Figure 3
Line chart of image 2

Figure is showing the expressions of respondents with text and emojis.

Table 7
Regression Analysis on Image 3

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.760 ^a	.779	.739	689.828

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q6b Image3;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"

This table also provides the R (correlation coefficient) and R2 values. The R-value expresses the simple correlation which is 0.760 so it is a high degree of correlation. The R2 conclude that 78% of the total variation in the Texts (dependent variable) representing by the Emoji (independent variable). The result indicates that variation is valid and people express their state of mind in texts with the 78% use of emojis.

Figure 4
Line chart of image 3

This figure also shows the state of mind of respondents with different text and emojis.

Table 8
Regression Analysis on image 4

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.667 ^a	.705	.691	732.777

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q7b Image4; Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"

This table also provides the R (correlation coefficient) and R2 values. The R-value expresses the simple correlation which is 0.667 so it is a high degree of correlation. The R2 concludes that 71% of the total variation in the Texts (dependent variable) is represented by the Emoji (independent variable). The result indicates that variation is valid, and people express their state of mind in texts with the 71% use of emojis.

Figure 5
Line chart of image 4

Table 9
Regression analysis on image 5

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.640 ^a	.657	.649	603.788

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q8b Image5;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"

This table indicates the R (correlation coefficient) and R² values. The R-value shows the simple correlation which is 0.640 so it is a strong degree of correlation. The R² exhibits that 66% of the total variation in the Texts (dependent variable) is the representation of the Emoji (independent variable). The result indicates that variation is valid, and people express their state of mind in texts with the 66% use of emojis.

Figure 6
Line chart on image 5

Table 10
Regression analysis on image 6

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.804 ^a	.837	.816	779.762

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q9b Image6; Express your state of mind using, "ONLY ONE EMOJI"

This table shows the R (correlation coefficient) and R² values. The R-value is expressing the simple correlation which is 0.804 so it is a high degree of correlation. The R² concludes that 84% of the total variation in the Texts (dependent variable) is represented by the Emoji (independent variable). The result indicates that variation is valid, and people express their state of mind in texts with 84% use of emojis.

Figure 7
Line chart on image 6

Hypothesis proposal and Hypothesis testing

For the statistical evidence, we proposed our hypothesis of each image separately so that we could know the significant value between emojis and text. This hypothesis test showed whether we should accept our H_0 or accept it. 6 Hypotheses tests are shown below: -

1. Image 1

- **Hypothesis:** H_0 = There is a positive significant effect of emojis on text messages
 H_1 = There is a negative significant effect of emojis on text messages
- **Level of significance:** $\alpha=0.05$
- **Test statistics:**

Paired Samples Test		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
Pair	Q4a Image1;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) - Q4b Image1;Express	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Mean	Lower				Upper
1	Q4a Image1;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) - Q4b Image1;Express	.22449	1.14137	.16305	-.10335	.55233	1.377	48	.175

your state of
mind using ,
"ONLY ONE
EMOJI"

- **Conclusion and discussion:** The column named mean is the mean difference between Q4a and Q4b which is 0.22449 and the column standard deviation is a difference of std. of Q4a and Q4b which is 1.14137. Here 't' gives the observed t value i.e. 1.377 with 48 degrees of freedom (df). The significant value is 0.175 which is greater than our level of significance i.e. 0.05. So the equation will be **p-value=0.175> α =0.05**, then according to this, we can conclude that we cannot reject our H_0 which implies that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the effect of emojis is positive on text messages.

2. Image 2

- **Hypothesis:** H_0 = There is a positive significant effect of emojis on text messages
 H_1 = There is a negative significant effect of emojis on text messages
- **Level of significance:** α =0.05
- **Test statistics:**

Paired Samples Test

Pair		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference Lower Upper			
1	Q5a Image2;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) - Q5b Image2;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"	-.16327	.82530	.11790	-.40032 .07379	-1.385	48	.173

The column named mean is the mean difference between Q5a and Q5b which is 0.16327 and the column standard deviation is a difference of std. of Q5a and Q5b which is 0.82530. Here 't' gives the observed t value i.e. 1.385 (we can ignore the sign) with 48 degrees of freedom (df). As we can see the significant value is 0.173 which is greater than our level of significance i.e. 0.05. So the equation will be **p-value=0.173 > α=0.05**, then according to this, we can conclude that we cannot reject our H₀ which implies that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the effect of emojis is positive on text messages.

3. Image 3

- **Hypothesis:** H₀= There is a positive significant effect of emojis on text messages
H₁= There is a negative significant effect of emojis on text messages
- **Level of significance:** α=0.05
- **Test statistics:**

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig.
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				(2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Paired Samples 1	Q6a	.3265	1.02851	.1469	.0311	.6219	1.22	4	.098
	Image3; Express your state of mind using , "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) - Q6b	3		3	1	5	2	8	
	Image3; Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"								

The column named mean is the mean difference between Q6a and Q6b which is 0.32653 and the column standard deviation is a difference of std. of Q6a and Q6b which is 1.02851. Here 't' gives the observed t value i.e. 1.222 with 48 degrees of freedom (df). As

we can see the significant value is 0.098 which is greater than our level of significance i.e., 0.05. So, the equation will be $p\text{-value}=0.098 > \alpha=0.05$, then according to this, we can conclude that we cannot reject our H_0 which implies that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the effect of emojis is positive on text messages.

4. Image 4

- **Hypothesis:** H_0 = There is a positive significant effect of emojis on text messages
 H_1 = There is a negative significant effect of emojis on text messages
- **Level of significance:** $\alpha=0.05$
- **Test statistics:**

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig.
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				(2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Paired Samples 1	Q7a - Q7b Image4;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) - Image4;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"	.6938	1.10310	.1575	.3770	1.0107	1.40	4	.130

- **Conclusion and discussion:** The column named mean is the mean difference between Q7a and Q7b which is 0.69388 and the column standard deviation is a difference of std. of Q7a and Q7b which is 1.10310. Here 't' gives the observed t value i.e. 1.403 with 48 degrees of freedom (df). As we can see the significant value is 0.130 which is greater than our level of significance i.e. 0.05. So the equation will be **p-value=0.130 > $\alpha=0.05$** , then according to this, we can conclude that we cannot reject our H_0 which implies that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the effect of emojis is positive on text messages.

5. Image 5

- **Hypothesis:** H_0 = There is a positive significant effect of emojis on text messages
 H_1 = There is a negative significant effect of emojis on text messages
- **Level of significance:** $\alpha=0.05$
- **Test statistics:**

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences	t	df	Sig.					
					Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower Upper	
Pair 1	Q8a - Image5;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) - Q8b Image5;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"	- .18367	1.18451	.16922	- .52390	.15656	- 1.085	48	.283

The column named mean is the mean difference between Q8a and Q8b which is 0.18367 and the column standard deviation is a difference of std. of Q8a and Q8b which is 1.18451. Here 't' gives the observed t value i.e. 1.085 (we can ignore the sign) with 48 degrees of freedom (df). As we can see the significant value is 0.283 which is greater than our level of significance i.e. 0.05. So the equation will be **p-value=0.283 > $\alpha=0.05$** , then

according to this, we can conclude that we cannot reject our H_0 which implies that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the effect of emojis is positive on text messages.

6. Image 6

- **Hypothesis:** H_0 = There is a positive significant effect of emojis on text messages
 H_1 = There is a negative significant effect of emojis on text messages
- **Level of significance:** $\alpha=0.05$
- **Test statistics:**

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference Lower Upper				
Pair 1	Q9a your state of mind using , "ONLY TEXT" (At-least one line) - Q9b Image6;Express your state of mind using , "ONLY ONE EMOJI"	-	.92398	.13200	-	.24499	-	48	.878
		.02041			.28581		.155		

The column named mean is the mean difference between Q9a and Q9b which is 0.02041 and the column standard deviation is a difference of std. of Q9a and Q9b which is 0.92398. Here 't' gives the observed t value i.e. 0.155 (we can ignore the sign) with 48 degrees of freedom (df). As we can see the significant value is 0.878 which is greater than our level of significance i.e. 0.05. So the equation will be $p\text{-value}=0.878 > \alpha=0.05$, then according to this, we can conclude that we cannot reject our H_0 which implies that there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the effect of emojis is positive on text messages.

4. Discussion

The study aims at the usage of emojis in text messages. The purpose of this study was to investigate the understanding of people regarding the use of emoticons and emojis. For this purpose, we developed our questionnaire and distributed it among 49 students who demonstrated their state of mind in texts and emojis. In this study, we presented our data graphically to elaborate on the demographic information of the students. To determine the correlation coefficient relationship between texts and emojis, we applied linear regression on 6 images individually.

According to the results of image 1, we came to know that 68% of the total variation in the texts was due to the Emojis, whereas 55% and 78% of the total variation in the texts was a representation of the Emoji in image 2 and image 3 respectively. Similarly, the results of image 4 showed 71%, image 5 concluded 66% and image 6 showed that 84% of the total variation in the texts was represented by the Emojis. So it is evident from the results that state of mind can be explained by the texts and there is always a need for emojis to support the text emotionally. The hypothesis testing for the evidence indicated the effect of emojis on text messages. The hypothesis testing conducted on 6 images individually concluded that emojis always have a positive effect on text messages when people describe their state of mind.

In our study, we used SPSS for all the analysis. The main tests in our study were regression analysis, correlations between variables and hypothesis testing. We applied simple linear regression analysis to know the correlation coefficients. This analysis showed a relationship between emojis and text messages. Moreover, we came to know the effects in percentages so that our study can tell the amount of effect of emojis on text messages. The results of regression analysis expectedly came very high. Therefore, according to the positive results of simple linear regression analysis there is a chance of acceptance of H_0 which is the evidence that emojis have a positive effect on text messages so for this purpose we performed hypothesis testing to know the significance value between emojis and text messages.

The problems under investigation were to analyse the effect of emojis on the semantics of language and to identify the understanding of emojis usage by the people to describe their state of mind. It confirms that emojis act as context clues and they assist the receiver to decode the sender's general attitude and the particular sentiment attached to it (Carroll, 2016).

A research conducted by Dürscheid and Siever (2017) for investigating an overview of the functions of emojis in everyday written communication affirms the first and second parts of our results which suggested that a considerable percentage of people are capable of explaining the semantics of language without the use of emojis and there are very fewer people who need emojis to say what they want to intend. Emojis are used as para verbal devices in communication and rarely replace the verbal parts of the messages. Emojis are just used to intensify the meanings of messages and they are seldom used as an independent channel of communication. The previous study by Kelly (2015) conducted on the understanding of emoticons and emojis used in text messages also claimed that emojis do not have a meaning in themselves.

The results of the present study are also in contradiction with a study by Novak, Sluban, and Mozetič, (2015) which asserts that emojis could be used as communication language as it completely describes the emotional state of the person. The understanding of the use of emojis was the third posed question of the present research. The findings of the research proposed that most of the people use emojis correctly to describe a state of mind which contrasts with the finding of Suresh (2018) who concluded that most of users are unaware of the correct use of emojis. This study comprised both aspects of communication including professional and non-professional aspects. So, the results differ because our sample people include only university students who use emojis more frequently in their communication compared to professionals. As far as the gender role is concerned, males are more likely to better understand the use of emojis to describe their state of mind than females who use emojis to describe the semantics of the language. This finding supports the study which states that men incorporate emojis in order to make their messages clear whereas women use emojis to illustrate a state of emotion the main function of emojis (Persson,2019).

Considering the findings and discussion, the present study concludes that though there is always a need for emojis to support the message emotionally, plain text without the use of any figure, object or letters can explain a major part of the semantics of the message.

References

1. Ai, W., Lu, X., Liu, X., Wang, N., Huang, G., & Mei, Q. (2017, April). Untangling emoji popularity through semantic embeddings. In Proceedings of the international AAAI conference on web and social media (Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 2-11).
2. Alshenqeeti, H. (2016). Are emojis creating a new or old visual language for new generations? A socio-semiotic study. *Advances in language and Literary Studies*, 7(6).
3. Arya, V., Sethi, D., & Verma, H. (2018). Are emojis fascinating brand value more than textual language? Mediating role of brand communication to SNS and brand attachment: An insight from India. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*.
4. Barach, E., Feldman, L. B., & Sheridan, H. (2021). Are emojis processed like words?: Eye movements reveal the time course of semantic processing for emoji-fied text. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 28, 978-991.
5. Barbieri, F., Kruszewski, G., Ronzano, F., & Saggion, H. (2016, October). How cosmopolitan are emojis? Exploring emojis usage and meaning over different languages with distributional semantics. In Proceedings of the 24th ACM international conference on Multimedia (pp. 531-535).
6. Barbieri, F., Ballesteros, M., & Saggion, H. (2017). Are emojis predictable?. arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.07285.
7. Beyersmann, E., Wegener, S., & Kemp, N. (2022). That's good news[®]: Semantic congruency effects in emoji processing. *Journal of Media Psychology: Theories, Methods, and Applications*.
8. Bliss-Carroll, N. L. (2016). The nature, function, and value of emojis as contemporary tools of digital interpersonal communication.
9. Debnath, A., Pinnaparaju, N., Shrivastava, M., Varma, V., & Augenstein, I. (2020, April). Semantic textual similarity of sentences with emojis. In Companion Proceedings of the Web Conference 2020 (pp. 426-430).
10. Grannan, C. (2017). What's the difference between emoji and emoticons. Retrieved from Britannica: <https://www.britannica.com/demystified/whats-the-difference-between-emoji->

- and-emoticons.
11. Grosz, P. G., Greenberg, G., De Leon, C., & Kaiser, E. (2023). A semantics of face emoji in discourse. *Linguistics and Philosophy*, 1-53.
 12. Hart, E. (2012). *The gilded masks of digital rhetoric: Social and pedagogical implications of evolving paralinguistic elements in web composition*. Western Carolina University.
 13. Hasyim, M. (2019). Linguistic functions of emoji in social media communication. *Opcion*, 35.
 14. Kelly, C. (2015). Do you know what I mean>:(A linguistic study of the understanding of emoticons and emojis in text messages.
 15. Kimura-Thollander, P., & Kumar, N. (2019, May). Examining the "global" language of emojis: Designing for cultural representation. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 1-14).
 16. Kralj Novak, P., Smailović, J., Sluban, B., & Mozetič, I. (2015). Sentiment of emojis. *PLoS one*, 10(12), e0144296.
 17. Liu, C., Fang, F., Lin, X., Cai, T., Tan, X., Liu, J., & Lu, X. (2021). Improving sentiment analysis accuracy with emoji embedding. *Journal of Safety Science and Resilience*, 2(4), 246-252.
 18. Logi, L., & Zappavigna, M. (2021). A social semiotic perspective on emoji: How emoji and language interact to make meaning in digital messages. *New Media & Society*, 14614448211032965.
 19. Lucas, G. (2016). *The story of emoji*. Prestel Verlag.
 20. Manganari, E. E. (2021). Emoji use in computer-mediated communication. *The International Technology Management Review*, 10(1), 1-11.
 21. Miller, H., Thebault-Spieker, J., Chang, S., Johnson, I., Terveen, L., & Hecht, B. (2016). "Blissfully happy" or "ready to fight": Varying interpretations of emoji. In *Proceedings of the international AAAI conference on web and social media* (Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 259-268).
 22. Natia Amaghlobeli (2012). Linguistic Features of Typographic Emoticons in SMS Discourse. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/6d9c/153f60718c38411b1bc0224aa95e62ff51c4.pdf>
 23. Novak, P. K., Smailović, J., Sluban, B., & Mozetič, I. (2015). Sentiment of emojis. *PLoS one*, 10(12).
 24. Persson, N. (2019). *Analysis of Emoji Usage: Differences in Preference and Function Across Genders*.
 25. Pfeifer, V. A., Armstrong, E. L., & Lai, V. T. (2022). Do all facial emojis communicate emotion? The impact of facial emojis on perceived sender emotion and text processing. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 126, 107016.
 26. Pohl, H., Domin, C., & Rohs, M. (2017). Beyond just text: semantic emoji similarity modeling to support expressive communication. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 24(1), 1-42.
 27. Qureshi, F., Gul, S., Akber, H., Qazi, Z., & Shakir, Z. (2021). An Analysis of the Emoji's Impact on the Language and Expressions of Youth on Social Media. *Ilkogretim Online*, 20(5), p2409-2425.
 28. Rotaru, A. S., & Vigliocco, G. (2020). Constructing semantic models from words, images, and emojis. *Cognitive science*, 44(4), e12830.
 29. Seyednezhad, S. M. M., Fede, H., Herrera, I., & Menezes, R. (2018, May). Emoji-word network analysis: sentiments and semantics. In *The Thirty-First International Flairs Conference*.
 30. Suresh, S. (2018). The influence of Emoji on Communication using Social Media-A Quantitative Study among College Students of Mysuru. *Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 9(1), 158-162.
 31. Tang, Y., & Hew, K. F. (2019). Emoticon, emoji, and sticker use in computer-mediated communication: A review of theories and research findings. *International Journal of Communication*, 13, 27.
 32. Tashakkori, A., & Teddlie, C. (2003). Issues and dilemmas in teaching research methods courses in social and behavioural sciences: US perspective. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 6(1), 61-77.
 33. Teddlie, C., & Tashakkori, A. (2009). *Foundations of mixed methods research: Integrating*

- quantitative and qualitative approaches in the social and behavioral sciences. Sage.
34. Walther, J. B., & D'addario, K. P. (2001). The impacts of emoticons on message interpretation in computer-mediated communication. *Social science computer review*, 19(3), 324-347.
 35. Wang, X., Cheng, M., Li, S., & Jiang, R. (2023). The interaction effect of emoji and social media content on consumer engagement: A mixed approach on peer-to-peer accommodation brands. *Tourism Management*, 96, 104696.
 36. Weissman, B., & Tanner, D. (2018). A strong wink between verbal and emoji-based irony: How the brain processes ironic emojis during language comprehension. *PloS one*, 13(8), e0201727.
 37. Wicke, P., & Bolognesi, M. (2020). Emoji-based semantic representations for abstract and concrete concepts. *Cognitive processing*, 21(4), 615-635.
 38. Wijeratne, S., Balasuriya, L., Sheth, A., & Doran, D. (2017, August). A semantics-based measure of emoji similarity. In *Proceedings of the international conference on web intelligence* (pp. 646-653).
 39. Wolf, A. (2000). Emotional expression online: Gender differences in emoticon use. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 3(5), 827-833.
 40. Yang, J., Yang, Y., Xiu, L., & Yu, G. (2022). Effect of emoji prime on the understanding of emotional words—evidence from ERPs. *Behaviour & information technology*, 41(6), 1313-1322.